

Results and Discussion

A few publications⁴⁻⁷ which contain electronic spectral information on U(V) species deal with this species in an octahedral or nearly octahedral environment. Four low energy transitions are predicted. These transitions can be denoted as $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$, $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_7'$, $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8'$ and $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_6$. But experimentally not only four bands rather four groups of bands are generally observed^{4,6,7}.

In the complexes $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ pyridine, $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ quinoline, $UCl_5 \cdot 3$ isoquinoline, $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ benzil and $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ anthrone, the $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8$ transition produces a weak band between 1650-1660 nm. The $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_7'$ transition produces a group of strong bands between 1435-1470 nm. The $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_8'$ transition exhibits two bands of roughly equal intensity at ~ 950 nm and ~ 1000 nm. The $\Gamma_7 \rightarrow \Gamma_6$ transition occurs between 850-870 nm in these complexes. Strong peaks between 600-700 nm and between 1050-1150 nm which are characteristic of U(IV) species^{8,9} were absent in UCl_5 complexes with nitrogen donors indicating that there is no disproportionation of U(V) into U(IV) and U(VI). However, in $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ benzil and $UCl_5 \cdot 2$ anthrone complexes a very strong band at ~ 1010 and ~ 1095 nm respectively indicates appreciable disproportionation of U(V) into U(IV) and U(VI) in complexes with oxygen donors.

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Relation Between the Lattice Energy and Melting Point of Alkali Hydroxides

M. M. HUSAIN, (MISS) A. GUPTA and D. K. SINGH

Chemistry Department, Lucknow University, Lucknow 226 007

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THE concept of lattice energy of similar class of compounds is an important consideration while dealing with different phenomena of chemical interest. For example, in a set of closely related substances it is invariably used to explain their solubility behaviour, relative thermal stability and the melting and boiling processes associated with them. Thus in latter instance, a direct proportionality between lattice energy (U_0) and absolute melting point (T_m) viz., $U_0/T_m \approx \text{const.}$, has been fairly established for a number of related systems including s, d and f block metals^{1,2}, molecular solids³⁻⁵ and ionic compounds^{6,7}. A similar correlation amongst the lattice energy and corresponding absolute boiling point (T_b) is also described elsewhere⁶⁻⁷.

The lattice energies of alkali hydroxides reported by different workers⁸⁻¹² appear to vary quite considerably. It was, therefore, thought desirable to examine the correspondence of existing lattice energy and melting point of these compounds for a ready approval of the former. In this attempt the relevant data^{8-12,13} along with observed U_0/T_m ratio are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RELATION BETWEEN U_0 AND T_m OF ALKALI HYDROXIDES*

Alkali Hydroxide	ref. 8	ref. 9	ref. 10	ref. 11	ref. 12	T_m (°K)
LiOH	215(0.30)	230(0.32)	229(0.32)	205(0.28)	205(0.28)	723
NaOH	205(0.35)	209(0.35)	196(0.33)	166(0.28)	176(0.30)	592
KOH	181(0.29)	184(0.29)	173(0.27)	145(0.23)	153(0.24)	634
RbOH	172(0.30)	174(0.30)	166(0.29)	137(0.24)	147(0.26)	573
CsOH	158(0.29)	165(0.30)	157(0.29)	130(0.24)	136(0.25)	546
Mean U_0/T_m	0.31	0.31	0.30	0.25	0.27	

* Values preceding parentheses are U_0 in K cal mole⁻¹ while those within parentheses refer to the observed ratio of U_0/T_m .

Table 1 reveals that the proportionality ratio between U_0 ⁸⁻¹⁰ and T_m ¹³ is fairly constant. The associated ratio for different alkali hydroxides is very close to 0.30. According to other sources of U_0 ^{11,12}, the U_0/T_m , however, give lower average values of 0.25 and 0.27 respectively. Thus, a much better correspondence between U_0 and T_m in the former as compared to latter appears to support the genuinity of U_0 data according to sources⁸⁻¹⁰, quite convincingly.

One would, likewise, expect a constancy of the ratio of U_0/T_b in the present system. In view of

the partial availability of boiling points in literature, it could, however, be only investigated for NaOH and KOH. The T_b data^{1,8} of the concerned (1663°K and 1593°K respectively) yield a value of $U_o/T_b \approx 0.12$ which may be assumed to be satisfactorily constant for the remaining members of alkali halides. With reference to U_o data^{11,12}, the ratio viz., $U_o/T_b \approx 0.10$ is again on a lower side to discredit these lattice energies. Further, using the relation $U_o/T_b \approx 0.12$, one may estimate the hypothetical boiling points of LiOH, RbOH and CsOH as being 1792°K, 1633°K and 1317°K respectively.

Moreover, the ratio of $U_o/T_m \approx 0.31$ observed in alkali hydroxides is almost twice as compared to the mean value of U_o/T_m for alkali halides⁶ (≈ 0.16). A similar trend of higher U_o/T_m with respect to U_o/T_b is pointed out in case of alkali halides as is maintained in this study as well.

Husain *et al*⁴, have established a constancy of the product of lattice energy (U_o) and equilibrium interionic distance (r_o) for the members of alkali halides. Applying this relation to another family of alkali hydroxides, the average $U_o r_o \approx 500$ K cal mole⁻¹ Å is obtained. $U_o r_o \approx 500$ in conjunction with the sum of ionic radii¹⁵ of Fr⁺ and OH⁻ ions ($r_o = 3.20$ Å) provides the U_o of FrOH to be 156 K cal mole⁻¹. A proper inclusion of this value in Table 1 tends to be a rational estimate along with the U_o ⁸⁻¹⁰ data of its preceding companions. This is what one should demand from the first principles.

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Acetylacetonanthranilic Acid as a Gravimetric Reagent for Zirconium

JESSY CHACKO and GEETHA PARAMESWARAN

Department of Chemistry, University of Calicut,
Calicut-673 635

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SEVERAL organic reagents have been tried¹⁻⁹ for the gravimetric determination of zirconium in its salts, alloys and ores. Very little work has been done with Schiff base complexes of Zr(IV) with anthranilic acid as the basic nucleus. O-mercaptoacetamidobenzoic acid, a derivative of anthranilic acid has been successfully used for the gravimetric estimation of Zr(IV)¹⁰ by Geetha and Padmini. N-acetylacetonanthranilic acid, a tridentate ligand was first prepared by Mehta et al for the estimation of copper¹¹. In the present note authors have described the use of N-acetylacetonanthranilic acid as a dependable reagent for zirconium.

The reagent was prepared by the condensation of acetylaceton and anthranilic acid in the presence of a few drops of piperidine¹¹. The reagent was characterised by its I.R. spectrum and elemental analyses. m.p. 162°. Equivalent weight was found out to be 208.

The reagent was used in the form of a 10% solution in 1:1 aqueous alcohol. 1 ml. of this solution is sufficient for the determination of 50 mg of ZrO₂. Only a slight excess of the reagent should be used since it is not highly soluble in water.

Zirconium can be conveniently determined in the range of 0.05-0.2 g. Zirconyl chloride solution was prepared in 0.1 N hydrochloric acid and standardised using mandelic acid as the precipitating agent⁴.

Procedure :

ZrOCl₂ solution (10 ml) was diluted to 150 ml. After adjusting the pH of the solution between 3.5 and 4.0 using ammonium acetate 10% hot solution (20 ml) of the reagent in 1:1 aqueous ethanol was added with constant stirring. The precipitate was digested for 30 min at 80-90° and cooled. It was filtered after 1 hr through Whatman filter paper No. 42, washed with a hot solution of the reagent, dried and ignited to constant weight in a platinum crucible and weighed as zirconium dioxide. The result obtained (0.1014 g) was in good agreement with the amount estimated with mandelic acid (0.1012 g).

Interference from other ions :

Zirconium was separated from aluminium(III), nickel(II), calcium(II), cerium(IV), uranyl(II), tin(IV), lead(II), germanium(IV), sulphate and nitrate ions when present to the extent of 25% of that of zirconium with an average relative error of